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STAGES OF URBANIZATION OF BUKHARA REGION

Бухоро вилоят ҳудудининг урбанизация босқичлари.

Этапы урбанизации Бухарской области.

Usmanov Muradxan Saidmaxmudovich¹, Akramov Doniyor Rustam o'g'li²

¹Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Urban Planning,
professor v.b., Uzbekistan.

²Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction, Foundation Doctorate (PhD),
Uzbekistan.

¹Toshkent Arxitektura qurilish universiteti, Shaharsozlik kafedrasini professor v.b., Uzbekistan.

²Toshkent Arxitektura qurilish universiteti, Tayanch Doktorant (PhD), Uzbekistan.

Annotation: This article describes the process of urbanization of the Republic of Uzbekistan and issues of their improvement and development. The current urbanization processes of the republic are described and they are grouped by regions, recommendations are given on the use of the current opportunities of the urbanization process of the regions. The progress of the urbanization process in Bukhara region was discussed. Some aspects related to the process of urbanization in the province and its districts are discussed

Keywords: cities, urbanization, grouping, city functions, monofunctional city, polyfunctional city, typology of cities

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi urbanizatsiya jarayoni va ularning takomillashtirish va rivojlantirish masalalari yoritilgan. Respublikaning hozirgi urbanizatsiya jarayonlari tavsif etilgan va ular hududlar kesimida guruhlashtirib chiqilgan, hududlarning urbanizatsiya jarayonining hozirgi kundagi imkoniyatlardan foydalanish bo'yicha tavsiyalar keltirilgan. Buxoro regionda urbanizatsiya jarayonining borishi to'g'risida fikr yuritilgan. Vилоят va uning tumanlarida urbanizatsiya jarayoni bilan bog'liq ayrim jihatlar to'g'risida so'z boradi

Kalit so'zlar: shaharlar, urbanizatsiya, guruhlashtirish, shaharfunktsiyalari, monofunksional shahar, polifunksional shahar, shaharlar tipologiyasi.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization, increasing urbanization process in countries and regions, their socio-economic development, the development of cities of different sizes and, in particular, large cities, towns, is a process that reflects the change in the lifestyle of the population. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 2019 No. PF

5623 "On measures to fundamentally improve the urbanization process" and the "Road" on the regulation of urbanization of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is attached to this decree It is important to carry out work based on the programs specified in the "map". The purpose of this decree is to increase the urbanization of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, the

urbanization process of Uzbekistan differs from region to region. (1)

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 155th among 203 countries in the world in terms of the level of urbanization. This indicator, in turn, has the same meaning as the indicator of population living in cities. The urbanization indicator of the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that it is lagging far behind the countries of the world.

Urbanization is a complex socio-economic process that covers all aspects and, at the same time, manifests differently in different countries. Its territorial features are formed under the influence of geographical location, natural conditions and resources, demographic situation, structure and specialization of economic sectors, transport, geo-ecological condition and other factors.

It is difficult to imagine the development of society, country and regions without the development of cities. Today, 50.8% of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan lives in cities and 49.2% in villages. This, in turn, determines the level of urbanization of the country. Currently, the rate of urbanization of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 50.8%. The urbanization process of the republic's territories differs from each other. The indicator of population

living in cities is higher in Namangan region than the republican indicator, while Khorezm region is much lower than the republican indicator (Figure 1). Figure 1 shows the urbanization of the Republic of Uzbekistan and all its regions [2]

Urbanized regions of Uzbekistan can be seen in the picture below. As of January 1, 2021, there were 120 cities and 1067 towns in the Republic of Uzbekistan. 17144.1 thousand people lived in them, and 16761.1 people lived in rural settlements (Fig. 1).

If at the previous stage the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoi and Tashkent regions took the lead in terms of the level of urbanization, then in the last period it was replaced by the densely populated Fergana Valley. The main reason for this is that Fergana Valley has a large population of large villages. District centers take the lead in increasing the potential of urbanization in the regions.

The process of urbanization in the regions differs from one another in that it is different in the regions. Based on this, it is possible to analyze the regions of the Republic by dividing them into groups depending on the level of urbanization (Table 1)

Table 1
 Grouping of the urbanization process by regions

	Grouping	The name of the regions
	The most urbanized hudud	Namangan region
	Urbanized area	Farg`ona region
		Andijon region
	A low urbanized area	Toshkent region
		Qoraqalpog`iston Respublikasi

		Navoiy region
		Jizzax region
		Qashqadaryo region
		Sirdaryo region
	The least urbanized area	Samarqand region
		Buxoro region
		Surxondaryo region
		Xorazm region

Source: Table compiled by the author

As of August 1, 2022, the population of Bukhara region was 1 million 990 thousand 400 people - this is the 9th place (out of 14) among the regions of Uzbekistan. The rural population is 62%, and the urban population is 38%

#	District name	District center
1	Olot district	Olot
2	Buxoro district	Galaosiyo
3	G'ijduvon district	G'ijduvon
4	Jondor district	Jondor (shaharcha)
5	Kogon district	Kogon
6	Qorako'l district	Qorako'l (shahar)
7	Qorovulbozor district	Qorovulbozor
8	Peshku district	Yangibozor
9	Romitan district	Romitan
10	Shofirkon district	Shofirkon
11	Vobkent district	Vobkent

Figure 1. Map of the districts (tuman) of the province (viloyat) of Bukhara in Uzbekistan²

Division: Olot (1), Bukhara (2), Vobkent (11), Gijduvan (3), Jondor (4), Kogon (5), Karakol (6), Qarovulbazar (7), Peshkun (8), Romitan (9), Shafirkon (10)

The dynamics of the demographic situation of the Bukhara region in January-September 2023 were analyzed by experts of the Center for Economic Research and Reforms, based on the preliminary report of the Statistics Agency. As of October 1, 2023, the number of permanent residents of the Bukhara region increased by 25.1 thousand people or 1.2% compared to the beginning of this year, and totaled 2,034,800 people. In particular, the urban population reached 750.7 thousand people (36.9% of the total population), and the rural population reached 1,284.1 thousand people (63.1% of

² Map of the districts (tuman) of the province (viloyat) of Bukhara in Uzbekistan

the total population). Bukhara region ranks 9th among the regions of the republic in terms of population. [3]

As of October 1 of this year, the distribution of the population was 1,020,300 men (50.1%), 1,014,500 (49.9%) women. Among them, the number of people below working age is 29.5%, working age is 57.5% and older than working age is 13.0%.

Looking at the cross-section of regions, the most populated areas in the region are Gijduvon district (321,300), Bukhara city (292,900) and Shofirkon district (186,000), Qarovulbazar district (19,800). , Kogon city (64.4 thousand) and Kogon district (84.0 thousand) districts are considered sparsely populated areas of the region. [2] [3]

As of October 1, 2023, the region has an average of 50.6 people per 1 square kilometer, Bukhara city (4,184.3 people), Kogon city (3,220.0 people) and Vobkent district (510, 3 people) is one of the most densely populated areas.

During January-September 2023, the number of births in the region was 34.2 thousand, the number of deaths was 6.5 thousand, the number of recorded marriages was 10.2 thousand, and the number of divorces was 1.9 thousand.

According to population migration, 6,000 people immigrated to the region for permanent residence, and 8,500 people moved from the region for permanent residence.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In this table 1, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan is divided into four groups depending on the indicator of living in cities, that is, the level of urbanization. The regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan were

taken into these groups, and the criterion of grouping was based on the country's urbanization index. As mentioned above, the level of urbanization of Uzbekistan is 50.8%. In the grouping of regions, four groups were formed on the basis of the republic indicator.

- The first most urbanized group is the level of urbanization above 60% territories;
- Second urbanized areas. Areas with a level of urbanization of 50-59%;
- The third least urbanized area. Areas with an urbanization level of 40-49%;
- The fourth least urbanized region. All areas with an urbanization rate below 39%.

Map of urbanized areas of Uzbekistan

Namangan region was included in the first group as the most urbanized region. Namangan region has the highest level of urbanization in the republic with 64.8%. The second urbanized group includes Fergana region and Andijan region, their urbanization level is 56.3% and 52.3%, respectively. The third group is low-urbanized regions, these groups include the main regions of the republic, that is, Tashkent region, Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoi region, Jizzakh region, Kashkadarya region and Surkhandarya regions. The fourth group, the lowest urbanized group, includes Samarkand region, Bukhara region, Surkhandarya region and Khorezm regions.

In 2009, taking into account the fact that the majority of the country's population lives in rural areas, in order to bring urban lifestyle and culture to them, and to improve infrastructure, the Cabinet of Ministers of 2009 "Additional measures to improve the administrative-territorial structure of the

Republic of Uzbekistan" according to the decision, 965 villages were granted township status. [4] [5]

The transformation of villages into towns was a unique new stage in the republic's urbanization (table 1). The population of the city in 2008 was 9.6 million. 14.3 million in 2009. people, the level of urbanization has increased to 50.8%. The highest rate was observed in Namangan region, 64.4%, in the second place - 58.7% in Fergana region, and in the third region Andijan - 53.1%. If analyzed from a theoretical point of view, the number of inhabitants and the fact that most of their family members are not employed in agriculture meet the requirements for the status of a town. However, in terms of urban infrastructure, architecture, urban culture, and lifestyle of the population, this is a form of "false urbanization". In most cases, the large number of cities, the presence of large cities and towns and urban agglomerations

indicate the high socio-economic potential of the region. According to the data of 2020, on average, one urban settlement was suitable for up to 0.38 thousand square kilometers in the republic. This indicator differs in different medical regions.

In 2009, more than a thousand towns were created on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan due to newly added towns. Fergana region has 197 towns, Kashkadarya region has 117, Namangan region has 115, and Surkhandarya region has 112. The lowest number of towns has 46 in Navoi region. , there are 26 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and 25 in the Syrdarya region. The urban settlements of the Republic of Uzbekistan are unevenly distributed across the regions of the country.

Table 2

Cities and towns of the Republic of Uzbekistan by region distribution (as of January 1, 2024)

No	Name of the area	Total cities	including the republic and region bo`ysunuvidagi	Townships
1.	Republic of Uzbekistan	120	32	1067
2.	Karakalpakstan Respublikasi	12	1	26
3.	Andijon region	11	2	79
4.	Buxoro region	11	2	68
5.	Jizzax region	6	1	42
6.	Kashkadarya region	12	2	117
7.	Navoiy region	7	3	46
8.	Namangan region	8	1	115
9.	Samarkand region	11	2	88

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistics Committee

The network of cities is also well developed in economic regions with high

demographic potential and relatively stable economy. The largest number of cities and towns belongs to the Fergana region (423), where 35.1% of the urban settlements of Uzbekistan are located. Also, South, Zarafshan and Tashkent economic regions

are relatively well provided with the number of cities. Currently, in the Lower Amudarya and Mirzachol regions, the economy of which has an agrarian-industrial direction, the network of cities is weak, and it is 8.2 and 6.8% of the urban system of the republic, respectively.

Among the cities of our country, only 1 millionaire city is the city of Tashkent, 2 very large cities with more than 500 thousand inhabitants are Namangan and Samarkand and 5 large cities, Andijan, Bukhara, Nukus, Fergana and Karshi, 10 large cities there are cities Ko'kan, Margilon, Termiz, Jizzakh, Navoi, Chirchik, Almalik, Angren, Urganch and Shahrisabz. There are 20 medium-sized cities and 50 medium-sized cities, and the remaining 32 are small cities. Among the 1078 towns, there are also towns that belong to the group of semi-medium cities and small towns according to the number of inhabitants, and most of them belong to the Fergana Valley region. In particular, there are more such towns in Andijan region than in other cities of the region. Buloqboshi, Baliqchi, Chinabad, Tortkol, Izboskan towns have a population of more than 20,000.

Below we consider the share of types of urban composition of regional cities according to population [5-4 b].

Of the total number of cities, "very large cities" accounted for 3.6%, "large cities" for 7.2%, "large cities" for 7.2%, medium-sized cities for 21.4%, "semi-medium-sized cities" " makes up 50%, and "small towns" make up 7.2%.

DISCUSSION

For the development of cities in countries and regions, it is desirable to have the appropriate number of cities. Next to a city with a population of 1 million, there

should be 2 cities with a population of 500,000, followed by 4 cities with a population of more than 250,000, and so on. Therefore, there are no cities in the region in accordance with this rule. This process is typical for our Republic and other regions.

In Uzbekistan, there are 25 cities subordinated to regions, 93 cities subordinated to districts, and the only capital city is subordinated to the republic. The region with the most cities is Tashkent region (16 cities), and Khorezm region has 3 cities with the fewest. After the structural changes in 2009, the total number of towns became 1079. Regions with the largest number of towns: 197 in Ferghana, 123 in Kashkadarya and 120 in Namangan. The number of towns is the least in the Syrdarya region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The urban settlements of the Republic of Uzbekistan are unevenly distributed across the country's regions. The network of economic regions with high demographic potential and relatively stable economy is also well developed. It will be possible to determine the level of urbanized areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the weight of cities. The largest number of cities belongs to the Fergana region (423), where 35.1% of the urban settlements of Uzbekistan are located. Also, South, Zarafshan and Tashkent economic regions are relatively well provided with the number of cities. At the moment, it can be seen that the urban network is weak in the Lower Amudarya and Mirzachol regions, which have an agrarian-industrial economy. The weight of the cities of Uzbekistan is determined by Figure 2, and the share of cities is analyzed in the cross-section of regions [6-12 b].

The indicator of the population of the city in the regions is given in the table above, and it can be seen that this indicator is different in each region. The share of urban population in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 32.9%. When the share of urban population is analyzed by region, it can be seen that Navoi region is 40.2%, Republic of Karakalpakstan is 40.1%, Tashkent region is 39.2%, Namangan region is 34.1% and it is higher than the republic indicator (2 – fig.).

In the weight of the city population, the population of the towns is not included, and it is compiled on the basis of the cities that have the status of a city. The population of the city with the republic indicator is 32.9%, Kashkadarya region with a lower indicator is 31.2%, Andijan region 27.8%, Fergana region 26.9%, Bukhara It can be seen that the region has 25%, Syrdaryo region 23.1%, Samarkand region 22.4%, Jizzakh region 22.3%, Surkhandarya region 16.3% and Khorezm region 13.6%.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion shows that the role of cities in the development of regions and the possibilities of development are very wide. As the level of urbanization increases, the regions develop slowly and continue to progress.

1. Building a green economy based on innovation in the region. Introduction of innovative technologies of "Smart City" in this direction

2. Urbanization and infrastructure development. In order to improve the living conditions of the population, it is decided to implement a number of measures to increase the level of urbanization of the region to 47% by 2026. In particular, in order to develop the processes of urbanization in

the Bukhara region, 1 large city (Bukhara city), 3 medium-sized cities (Kogon, G'izhduvon, Karakol) and 2 small towns (Yangibozor and Gazli) will be phased in 2019-2030. stage development is planned.

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